

Economic Sciences

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**FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF YOUNG
PROFESSIONALS IN TRANSPORTATION**

Abstract: The development trend shows that among the factors influencing the development of society at the present time, the formation of competitive qualities in young people plays an important role. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the factors influencing the formation of competitive qualities in young people. The article discusses the ongoing reforms in the transport sector in Uzbekistan, the training of competitive personnel for the transport sector. An analysis of the results of a sociological survey conducted among students and employees working in this field.

Keywords: professional competitive qualities, competitiveness, need and motivation, knowledge and skills, level of development, professional orientation.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been carrying out large-scale reforms in all spheres of society. In particular, attention is paid to the effective use of available resources to achieve a quality and comfortable appearance of railway transport services to the population in accordance with modern requirements. This is especially true in the field of passenger transport. Instead of railways that do not meet the requirements of modern technical development, modern high-speed Afrasiab, Eastern expressways serve the population. The launch of new lines and the opening of the Angren-Pop route will have a positive impact on the content of railway transport services for passengers, as well as make it more important to ensure the

competitiveness of young professionals in the field. After all, the prospects for the development of any industry depend on the competitiveness of professionals working and trained in this field.

Uzbekistan Railways will introduce innovative projects to build new roads, reconstruct major railways and ensure traffic safety, localize import-substituting parts, create new jobs, as well as train modern knowledgeable personnel for the industry. It is no coincidence that the government pays special attention to the creation of appropriate conditions for this and the successful solution of other social issues.

Radical improvement of the system of training highly qualified personnel for the transport sector of Uzbekistan on the basis of advanced foreign experience and international standards, wide introduction of innovative forms and methods of teaching in the educational process and modern pedagogical and information technologies are important. Taking into account the demand for qualified personnel among enterprises of Uzbekistan, as well as strengthening the material and technical base and further increasing the scientific potential of the sector's educational institutions is essential. On May 4, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures to radically improve the system of training in transport"[1]. It includes the main tasks and activities of the university:

1. Training, retraining and advanced training of competitive higher education specialists and scientific and pedagogical staff, as well as mass professionals in the labor market, based on the needs of the transport sector;

2. Carrying out fundamental, applied and innovative research and studies on topical issues of development of the transport sector, the development of proposals for their results, including the widespread introduction of digital and other modern technologies;

3. Creation of a continuous system of training for the transport sector, ensuring consistent educational programs in the system of academic lyceums and professional educational institutions of the industry;

It is important to ensure that theoretical training is inextricably linked with practice in the educational process, together with organizations in the field of transport to organize student internships in relevant organizations [3, p.495-500; 4, p.2759-2762].

Sociological research was conducted on the basis of two different questionnaires in three directions. The object of research is students of Tashkent State Transport University, as well as teachers and staff of Tashkent Railway Vocational College, Samarkand Railway Vocational College, Kokand Railway Vocational College and the Tashkent State Transport University, Training Road Center” listeners, 400 respondents were selected [2, p.223].

"Do you think your level of knowledge is sufficient for the work you are doing?" 39% of the respondents who participated in the survey indicated that they fit, 16% said that they did not fit completely, 13% said that they did not know exactly, and 32% said that they did not fit completely. That is, they said they were not working in the specialty they graduated from (Figure 1). Of course, this situation affects the work and mentality of the specialist. It undermines his level of professional flexibility and leads to job dissatisfaction. Professional psychophysiological flexibility is extended by the specialist over a long period of time. It also has a negative impact on labor productivity.

The study also asked, “What methods are used in your organization or institution to increase professional growth?” with the question, we tried to determine what methods organizations use to strengthen the morale of professionals and their positive attitudes towards activities. Twenty-five percent of respondents identified free education as a two-month in-service training course, while 23 percent of respondents reported an increase in discharge. While the opportunity to raise the service sector was 18%, rewards and moral incentives accounted for 16% (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Do you consider your level of knowledge sufficient for the work you are doing?

The results of the study show that while spiritual motivation is important in organizations, it is given less attention. Many people want their hard work to be appreciated and at least expect spiritual encouragement. If these circumstances are not taken into account, the alienation of workers, employees and professionals from the labor process will increase. As the process of alienation deepens, so does its prevention and treatment. Of course, this situation also affects the efficiency of the work.

When respondents were asked about the professional and work-related qualities of professionals, 63.6% said they considered their competence satisfactory, 40.9% said they were polite and kind, 45.5% said they treated passengers, and 59.1% said they were general. Regarding the satisfactory rate 31.8% of respondents said that they were fully satisfied with the competence, 36.4% said that they were polite and kind, 45.5% said that they treated the passengers, and 27.3% said that they were satisfied with the overall work. Those who considered it insufficient were 4.5% for communication competence, 18.2% for politeness and benevolence, and 4.5% for passenger attitude, and 9.1% for overall work impression. Those who did not respond reported 4.5% for all qualities (Figure 3).

Figure 2. What methods are used to increase the professional growth trend in your organization or institution?

It is obvious that professional and work-related qualities that are not at a professional level cannot fully meet today's demand. This is not enough, especially if we look at the level of passenger service in the railway sector, which is even lower than 50%. It would be expedient to develop a clear system for the complete formation of service labels in this area. Because there are short courses and less hours are devoted to ethics and etiquette. It is well known that ethical issues are related to the sign of humanity and its qualitative criteria. The demand and need for spiritually high and enlightened, cultured professionals is growing from year to year. The railway industry is no exception. Despite the modernization in this area, it is clear that the reforms will not be effective without a high-quality person.

Figure 3. How do you assess the professional and work-related qualities of railway workers?

In conclusion, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following main directions of solving these problems:

- The basis of personnel policy should be the development of the strategy of the organization (institution, firm, corporate) for five or more years in the management of "human resources" and the development of human capital. This means the use of human resources, its renewal and improvement, the development of motivation.

- Personnel strategy shows that structural changes in the labor market should take into account the characteristics of the workforce at the global, national and regional levels;

- The use of "human resources" and "human capital" of JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" based on the needs and requirements for personnel in the training of young professionals working in the field of transport, with the development of accurate forecasts for the next 5 years or more is advisable to develop optimal options;

- It is expedient to ensure the competitiveness of young professionals working in the field of transport by retraining and constantly improving their skills by improving the system of labor motivation and incentives through the introduction of new methods and forms of human resource management.

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